

MethaneSAT Level-4 Dispersed Emissions Product: Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document v1.1

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1 Introduction

The MethaneSAT Level-4 (L4) dispersed emissions product is an estimate of methane emissions within a MethaneSAT scene, reported on a $4\text{ km} \times 4\text{ km}$ grid and representative of a scene-dependent temporal window of up to 28 h before the observation.

MethaneSAT L4 emissions estimates are generated using the Column Observations to Regional Emissions (CORE) algorithm, a computational framework that integrates MethaneSAT observations with atmospheric transport modeling within a Bayesian inversion.

This Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD) describes the theoretical formulation, assumptions, data inputs, and implementation of CORE. It does not provide validation or usage instructions.

1.1 MethaneSAT

MethaneSAT is a spaceborne imaging spectrometer operating in a sun-synchronous low-Earth orbit and mounted on a spacecraft bus capable of targeted scene acquisition. It collected data from 4 March 2024 until a critical failure on 20 June 2025. MethaneSAT measured column-averaged dry-air mole fractions of methane (XCH_4) over scenes covering $220\text{ km} \times 220\text{ km}$ with ground pixels measuring $110\text{ m} \times 400\text{ m}$ (at nadir¹). MethaneSAT observations enable detection and quantification of methane emissions from larger distinct sources and the distribution of smaller sources in aggregate (“dispersed” sources), enabling estimation of total regional emissions. MethaneSAT scenes primarily targeted oil and gas production to characterize global emissions from the oil and gas production industry (Williams et al., 2025a,b), though a variety of other methane sources have also been imaged.

At each pixel, the MethaneSAT instrument recorded reflected solar spectra in the shortwave infrared, resolving methane absorption features near $1.6\ \mu\text{m}$ with a spectral dispersion of 0.08 nm per pixel and a spectral resolution of 0.23 nm (full width at half maximum). Methane column retrievals (Chan Miller et al., 2024) employ a carbon-dioxide proxy method (Butz et al., 2010) to measure XCH_4 . Single-pixel random $1\text{-}\sigma$ precision ranges from 25 ppb to 55 ppb, depending on surface albedo and viewing geometry. Aggregation to $2\text{ km} \times 2\text{ km}$ spatial scales improves precision to approximately 2.5 ppb to 5.5 ppb. These aggregated XCH_4 observations form the primary input to CORE.

1.2 Column Observations to Regional Emissions (CORE)

CORE estimates methane emissions from MethaneSAT XCH_4 observations using a Bayesian inverse modeling framework. The method combines observed methane concentrations with a forward model that uses a Jacobian matrix to relate surface fluxes to observed enhancements in XCH_4 . The forward model predicts satellite observations from surface emissions, boundary inflow, and background. These quantities are inferred by sampling their posterior distribution using a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) approach, providing both emission estimates and their associated uncertainties.

CORE incorporates several features designed for robust and automated emission estimation. These include a spatially uniform emissions prior, enforced non-negativity of fluxes, and automatic separation of background XCH_4 from enhancements. The algorithm is fully automated, with optional user inputs for domain definition and model hyperparameters. Its primary output is a gridded map of posterior emission estimates with associated uncertainty, reported over regions with sufficient information content. Total scene emissions and uncertainties are obtained by summing all reported emitters.

1.3 Workflow

The CORE workflow, summarized in Figure 1, transforms MethaneSAT Level-3 (L3) observations into gridded methane emission estimates through a sequence of data processing, transport modeling, and inversion steps.

Figure 1: Schematic workflow for the Column Observations to Regional Emissions (CORE) algorithm. External Inputs are green, procedures are blue, intermediate products are gray, and the output is red.

XCH_4 observations are provided to CORE from the MethaneSAT L3 product. The L3 product is a raster of oversampled XCH_4 derived using the physics-based oversampling method of (Sun et al., 2018). See Table 2 for information about the L3 fields used in CORE.

L3 observations are regridded to the CORE observation grid (defined on a Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projection) and aggregated prior to the inversion, as described in XCH_4 Observations.

The Jacobian matrix, which quantifies the source-receptor relationship between surface methane emissions and XCH_4 enhancements on the observation grid, is then computed using atmospheric transport simulated by the Stochastic Time-Inverted Lagrangian Transport (STILT; Fasoli et al., 2018; Lin, 2003) model driven by meteorological fields from the Global Forecast System (GFS) (Shen et al., 2023), as described in Atmospheric Transport Modeling.

The Jacobian matrix is pre-processed by applying emitter Model Domains, including treatment of exterior emitters in preparation to compute the Inflow.

A background that captures variability in air mass, the vertical distribution of atmospheric methane, and instrument sensitivity is computed by comparing observed XCH_4 to expected variations in the MethaneSAT Level-2 (L2) retrieval prior. Details can be found in Background.

Surface methane emissions are then estimated using Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) sampling implemented in the Stan probabilistic programming framework (Carpenter et al., 2017). The inversion produces posterior emission estimates and associated uncertainties, which are reported as gridded emission maps, as described in Posterior Sampling.

2 Forward Model

The forward model simulates MethaneSAT XCH₄ as the sum of contributions from surface methane emissions and background atmospheric variability. The model parameters are estimated using the Hamiltonian Monte Carlo procedure described in Posterior Sampling.

The forward model is linear and expressed as:

$$\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{J}_{\text{int}}\mathbf{s}_{\text{int}} + \mathbf{J}_{\text{ext}}\mathbf{s}_{\text{ext}} + (\mathbf{z}_{\text{prior}} + \mathbf{A}b). \quad (1)$$

Table 1 defines the symbols in Equation 1. The inferred model parameters are the surface methane fluxes s_{int} and s_{ext} and the background offset b . The following sections describe each component of the forward model in detail.

Table 1: Symbols of Equation 1

Symbol	Unit	Dimension	Description
\mathbf{z}	ppb	n	MethaneSAT XCH ₄ observation, aggregated 2 km × 2 km pixels
$\mathbf{J}_{\text{int}}, \mathbf{J}_{\text{ext}}$	ppb kg ⁻¹ h ⁻¹	$n \times m, n \times k$	Jacobian matrices describing sensitivity to interior emissions and exterior inflow
$\mathbf{s}_{\text{int}}, \mathbf{s}_{\text{ext}}$	kg h ⁻¹	m, k	Surface methane fluxes in the interior domain and pseudo-fluxes in the exterior (inflow) domain
$\mathbf{z}_{\text{prior}}$	ppb	n	Level-2 product prior estimate of XCH ₄ concentration
b	ppb	1	Background offset applied to Level-2 product prior estimate of XCH ₄ concentration
\mathbf{A}	dimensionless	n	Retrieval averaging kernel

2.1 XCH₄ Observations

The MethaneSAT L3 product provides XCH₄ on a regular latitude-longitude grid with a spatial resolution of approximately 45 m. These grid cells are referred to as L3 observation pixels.

L3 observations are aggregated to 2 km × 2 km pixels (L4 observation pixels) prior to inversion. This reduces the number of observations by approximately two orders of magnitude, limiting the computational cost of both the inversion and Jacobian generation while reducing measurement noise. The procedure consists of the following aggregation and filtering steps:

1. **Point spread function coverage requirement:** L3 observations are retained only if $n_{\text{samples}} > 0.1$, where n_{samples} represents the fractional coverage of the spectrometer point spread function.
2. **Aggregation:** For each L4 observation pixel, XCH₄ is computed as the unweighted arithmetic mean of contributing L3 observation pixels.
3. **L4 observation pixel coverage requirement:** An L4 observation pixel is retained only if at least 50% of the expected L3 pixels within the 2 km × 2 km area pass the filtering criteria.

Figure 2 illustrates the effect of aggregation from L3 to L4 resolution and the resulting spatial coverage after filtering. The aggregation reduces noise and data volume while preserving the dominant spatial structure of XCH₄ enhancements. The aggregated XCH₄ values form the observation vector \mathbf{z} .

Figure 2: MethaneSAT L3 XCH_4 (left) and MethaneSAT L3 XCH_4 aggregated to the L4 grid and filtered for use in CORE (right). Regions of clouds and extreme topography where observation coverage is below 50% are discarded. Collection taken in California USA, 12 November, 2024 @ 22:14:46 UTC.

2.2 Atmospheric Transport Modeling

CORE computes source-receptor sensitivities using the Stochastic Time-Inverted Lagrangian Transport model (STILT) (Fasoli et al., 2018; Lin, 2003). These sensitivities form the Jacobian matrix that links variations in observed XCH_4 to upwind methane emissions and inflow.

STILT is a Lagrangian Particle Dispersion Model (LPDM) widely used in inverse modeling of trace gases² (Gerbig et al., 2003; He et al., 2018; Lin et al., 2004; Miller et al., 2013; Pillai et al., 2012). In this framework, atmospheric transport is simulated by releasing particles from the observation location and time (the receptor) and tracking their trajectories backward in time. Particle motion is driven by advection from resolved meteorological winds and stochastic diffusion representing unresolved turbulence.

Backward particle trajectories define a surface influence function (footprint) that quantifies the sensitivity of each observation to upwind emissions. These influence functions are assembled into the Jacobian matrix used in the forward model.

STILT represents atmospheric transport at scales finer than those resolved by the meteorological input through the stochastic motion of particles. This sub-grid formulation is essential because MethaneSAT observations resolve spatial variability in XCH_4 at scales finer than those represented in current global meteorological products. It enables the inversion to retain sensitivity to localized methane sources, while emissions are ultimately reported on a $4\text{ km} \times 4\text{ km}$ grid.

2.2.1 Meteorological Inputs

Publicly available MethaneSAT L4 emissions products are generated using STILT driven by meteorological inputs from the Global Forecast System (GFS) (GFS, 2026; Bengtsson and Han, 2024) produced by the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA).

GFS is used as the baseline meteorological input for the following reasons:

1. **Global coverage:** The model provides consistent meteorological fields worldwide, allowing all MethaneSAT L4 products to be generated using the same transport framework.
2. **Public availability:** GFS data are openly available in the NOAA Air Resources Laboratory (ARL) format via the READY Gridded Data Archives and in General Regularly-distributed Information in Binary (GRIB) format via the NOAA Operational Model

Archive and Distribution System (NOMADS). This allows independent users to reproduce MethaneSAT transport simulations using STILT or related models.

3. **Established use:** GFS has a long history of use in atmospheric transport modeling and inverse analyses and is well validated (e.g., Bhargava et al., 2018; Gaudet et al., 2024).

CORE also supports meteorological inputs from several alternative models, including the NOAA Global Ensemble Forecast System (GEFS), The NOAA High-Resolution Rapid Refresh Model (HRRR), and the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) ENS.

2.2.2 STILT Implementation

CORE uses a custom configuration of STILT that supports efficient generation of Jacobian matrices for satellite observations.

The Jacobian matrix \mathbf{J} has dimensions $n_r \times n_e$ where n_r is the number of receptors and n_e is the number of emitters. Each element $\mathbf{J}_{r,e}$ represents the sensitivity of observation r to emissions from location e , expressed in units ppb per (kg h^{-1}). Receptors span the observed domain, while emitters extend up to 300 km beyond the observed area.

CORE uses STILT receptor volumes extending over a $2 \text{ km} \times 2 \text{ km}$ L4 observation pixel (see XCH₄ Observations) and a specified vertical layer in the atmospheric model. Each vertical layer is defined as a range of heights in meters above ground level (AGL). Nineteen vertical layers extend from the surface to 10,000 m AGL, with boundaries: [0, 30, 80, 140, 200, 300, 400, 600, 800, 1000, 1400, 1800, 2300, 2900, 3500, 4500, 5500, 7000, 8500, 10000].

For each receptor volume, 150 particles are initialized within the volume at the observation time and transported backward in time. The particles are distributed uniformly within the receptor volume. The choice of 150 particles represents a compromise between computational cost and variance in the estimated footprint. Increasing particle count beyond this value produces diminishing returns in Jacobian accuracy.

Particles are transported backward for 28 hours or until they leave the model domain (see Model Domains). Within this time window, receptors located above 10,000 m AGL produce negligible surface influence. Extending the integration beyond 28 hours produces negligible additional surface influence for most receptors.

STILT footprints are computed for the ensemble of particle trajectories from each receptor volume and integrated by a weighted sum with weights derived from the pressure fraction of dry air in the atmosphere and the MethaneSAT averaging kernel (see Averaging Kernel Dependency).

CORE includes pre-processing tools that extract only the meteorological variables required for the transport simulation and crop the extent to the modeling domain. The variables include horizontal wind velocity, vertical velocity, temperature, pressure, planetary boundary layer height, and surface flux parameters. This pre-processing step reduces the size of a typical meteorological input file from approximately 3 GB to approximately 10 MB, which improves computational efficiency during Jacobian generation, enabling parallel processing on approximately 1,000 nodes.

2.3 Averaging Kernel Dependency

MethaneSAT XCH₄ observations are derived from the L2 retrieval and do not represent the true atmospheric methane column directly. Instead, the retrieval has a vertical sensitivity that varies with pressure and observation conditions. This sensitivity is described by the methane column averaging kernel.

The averaging kernel A_i quantifies the sensitivity of the retrieved methane column to changes in the true methane partial column in atmospheric layer i . It represents the derivative of the

retrieved column concentration with respect to the true partial column:

$$A_i = \frac{\partial p}{\partial z_{true,i}} \quad (2)$$

where both quantities are expressed in units of column abundance (mol cm^{-2}). The averaging kernel is dimensionless, although its units may be written as mol cm^{-2} per mol cm^{-2} to indicate its physical interpretation.

MethaneSAT CH_4 averaging kernels typically range from approximately 0.5 to 1.1, with higher sensitivity generally occurring over high-albedo surfaces. Figure 3 illustrates an example of the averaging kernel for MethaneSAT. From ground level to the mid-troposphere, the averaging kernel is well-approximated by a linear function of height AGL. CORE computes the Jacobian using two column sums vertically weighted by the coefficients of the linear approximation, which are then added together. This simplification preserves the dominant features of the vertical structure while substantially reducing storage and computational requirements in the Jacobian.

Figure 3: Example of the methane (CH_4) column averaging kernel for one MethaneSAT pixel (black) demonstrating the linear relationship from the surface to the mid-troposphere (red).

2.4 Model Domains

CORE constrains surface methane emissions within several spatial domains defined using MethaneSAT observations and the source-receptor sensitivities represented by the Jacobian matrix. The data domain consists of regions with valid observations. This domain defines two additional regions: the interior domain, where emissions are directly constrained by nearby observations, and the exterior domain, which includes surrounding areas that may influence the observations through atmospheric transport.

2.4.1 Data Domain

L3 files may contain invalid observations, for example over clouds or water. Observations within 1,000 m of missing data are also excluded to reduce errors related to cloud and surface filtering.

Cloud cover may fragment the observations into multiple disconnected regions. CORE identifies contiguous regions of valid observations and selects the largest region with an area of

at least $7,500 \text{ km}^2$ as the initial data domain. If no region meets this threshold, the minimum area requirement is reduced iteratively.

Additional disconnected regions (“data islands”) may be included if they are sufficiently large or close to the main region. This step accounts for both cloud-induced fragmentation and true geographic islands, which may have distinct methane inflow conditions. A candidate island is included if its area represents at least 20% of the additional area required to expand the convex hull of the existing data domain to include it. Otherwise, the island is excluded.

Figure 4 illustrates the data domain selection procedure. The largest contiguous region of valid observations is first identified, and additional disconnected regions are included only if they contribute significantly to the spatial extent of the domain. This ensures that the inversion operates on a coherent observational region while retaining nearby data islands that may influence inflow.

Figure 4: Illustration of the data domain selection. MethaneSAT XCH₄ observations are shown in gray scale. The algorithm starts by including the largest contiguous observed region (cyan). Additional disconnected regions are included if they are sufficiently large or close to the main region. The five largest data domain areas are colored, the smaller ones are black. Note that three large data islands are excluded: two correspond to geographic islands in the south, and one region in the northwest is separated from the main domain by cloud cover. Collection taken in California USA, 12 November, 2024 @ 22:14:46 UTC.

2.4.2 Interior Domain

The interior domain is the region where surface methane fluxes are directly constrained by nearby observations. It is derived from the data domain by removing all data gaps and applying a morphological closing operation to connect nearby regions within the observation region. Surface fluxes within the interior domain are estimated on a $4 \text{ km} \times 4 \text{ km}$ grid.

2.4.3 Exterior Domain

The exterior domain is the domain where CORE computes “pseudo-fluxes” to simulate the inflow.

STILT computes Jacobian footprints for emitters within 300 km of the interior domain boundary. Although this definition initially produces an exterior domain larger than the interior, only upwind locations contribute to the observed signal.

The source-receptor sensitivity is used to refine the exterior domain. Cells are removed in order of increasing influence until the cumulative excluded influence reaches 4% of the total. This procedure typically removes about 75% of exterior cells, as most downwind locations have negligible influence on the observations. The Inflow section describes how exterior emitter cells are treated differently from those in the interior domain.

2.4.4 Reported Domain

The reported domain is the subset of the interior domain for which emission estimates are reported. Interior emitters located within 1,900 m of the outflow boundary are excluded, as emissions in these regions are insufficiently constrained by observations.

The reported domain is defined as the intersection of the interior domain and the region covered by the Jacobian, followed by an inward buffer of 1,900 m from the outflow boundary.

Figure 5 shows the relationship between the data, interior, exterior, and reported domains. The interior domain defines where emissions are estimated, while the exterior domain captures upwind influence through atmospheric transport. The reported domain excludes regions near the outflow boundary where emissions are weakly constrained.

Figure 5: Emitter domains derived from the data domain shown in Figure 4. The data domain is highlighted in orange. It defines the interior domain and the exterior domain, which includes both non-clustered and clustered emitter cells (dark to bright blue). The reported domain is outlined in black. Thin black lines delineate emitter cells, illustrating the resolution and the clustering applied in the exterior domain. Collection taken in California USA, 12 November, 2024 @ 22:14:46 UTC.

2.5 Extraneous Contributions to XCH₄

The forward model separates observed XCH₄ into contributions from interior emissions and non-local components. The non-local contribution consists of background and inflow:

$$\mathbf{J}_{\text{ext}}\mathbf{s}_{\text{ext}} + (\mathbf{z}_{\text{prior}} + \mathbf{A}b) \quad (3)$$

These terms account for two components:

1. **The background**, represented by the prior XCH₄, $\mathbf{z}_{\text{prior}}$ with an offset $\mathbf{A}b$.
2. **The inflow**, represented by emissions outside the interior domain that influence the observations through atmospheric transport ($\mathbf{J}_{\text{ext}}\mathbf{s}_{\text{ext}}$).

2.5.1 Background

The background ($\mathbf{z}_{\text{prior}} + \mathbf{A}b$) represents the expected XCH₄ in the absence of any emitter sources in the interior or exterior domains. Posterior emissions are (to first order) directly proportional to the enhancement above background ($\mathbf{z} - (\mathbf{z}_{\text{prior}} + \mathbf{A}b)$) and are therefore sensitive to the background estimate.

The prior XCH₄ ($\mathbf{z}_{\text{prior}}$) used in the MethaneSAT L2 retrieval (Laughner et al., 2023) accounts for large-scale factors that influence XCH₄. These include topographic variations in air mass and the vertical distribution of methane in the atmosphere, as well as the meridional gradient in methane concentration that increases toward the equator, and seasonal variations associated with the annual methane growth rate. Across a typical MethaneSAT scene, the latter two effects vary only weakly.

A mean difference (bias) between the prior and the retrieved XCH₄ is common. CORE therefore applies an additive background offset b . This offset is assumed to be vertically uniform but is scaled by the column averaging kernel \mathbf{A} . Typical values of b range within ± 20 ppb.

The background offset, b , is represented on a triangular mesh covering the scene. Each mesh element has an approximate area of 400 km². Although the background offset is represented on a coarse spatial mesh, strong regularization constrains it to vary slowly across the scene, such that it behaves approximately as a single scene-wide parameter.

This background model is independent of the emissions sources estimated by CORE. The Background Offset section describes how the offset parameter b is inferred from the observations.

Figure 6 shows the aggregated XCH₄ field and the corresponding enhancement above background.

2.5.2 Inflow

Inflow represents methane variability transported into the reported domain from upwind sources and meso- to synoptic-scale atmospheric structure. It is represented in the inversion by “pseudo-fluxes” in the exterior domain, which are treated analogously to emissions but are not individually identifiable from true emissions due to similarities in their observational influence.

As methane is transported downwind, emission plumes disperse and their spatial structure becomes smoother. Consequently, exterior emissions primarily contribute low-frequency variability to the observed XCH₄ field, with the effective spatial scale increasing with distance from the domain boundary. Deeper within the interior domain, inflow influences are therefore limited to progressively longer-wavelength structure, while shorter-wavelength variability is increasingly dominated by local emissions. In this sense, inflow acts as a spatial filter with a transport-dependent cutoff scale, such that the effective high-pass threshold becomes more restrictive with increasing distance from the boundary.

The Jacobian typically contains more exterior than interior emitter cells, even when restricted to upwind regions. Many distant exterior emitters produce similar influence patterns

Figure 6: Original Caption: MethaneSAT L3 XCH₄ observations aggregated to the L4 grid (left), with fitted XCH₄ background (center) and the resulting XCH₄ enhancement (right). The same color scale is used for the observations and background to accurately represent the data, while the legend ticks in the background plot show the minimum and maximum background. Collection taken in California USA, 12 November, 2024 @ 22:14:46 UTC.

on the observations, resulting in near-collinearity and making their individual contributions difficult to distinguish.

To address this, CORE aggregates exterior emitters into clusters. The native 4 km × 4 km resolution is retained for emitters within 5 km of the interior domain boundary, where spatial detail is most important. Emitters farther from the boundary are grouped using k-means clustering based on the cosine similarity of their Jacobian footprints, forming larger effective emitter cells. This approach emphasizes similarity in footprint structure rather than magnitude. Empirical analysis indicates that approximately 350 clusters provide a suitable balance between model complexity and the ability to represent inflow variability.

3 Inversion Framework

CORE estimates surface methane emissions by solving the inverse problem defined in Equation (1) using a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) approach. This method samples from the posterior distribution of the model parameters given the observations and prior information.

Compared with point-estimate methods such as maximum a posteriori optimization, MCMC provides expectation values of inferred parameters and a fuller characterization of both their marginal and joint uncertainties.

CORE generates posterior samples using the Stan probabilistic programming framework (Carpenter et al., 2017).

3.1 Posterior Sampling

Stan implements the No-U-Turn Sampler (NUTS; Hoffman and Gelman, 2011), an adaptive variant of Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC; Neal, 2011). These methods efficiently explore high-dimensional posterior distributions with minimal manual tuning and provide diagnostics for detecting biased estimation or incomplete exploration of the parameter space (Betancourt, 2018).

The inversion estimates model parameters by sampling from the posterior distribution $p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|z)$ where z is the vector of observed XCH₄ values and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ represents the model parameters. In CORE, the parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ consists of:

- surface emission rates \mathbf{s} , and
- the background offset parameter b .

Applying Bayes’ theorem, the posterior density is proportional to the product of the likelihood and the prior:

$$p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{z}) \propto p(\mathbf{z}|\boldsymbol{\theta}) \cdot p(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad (4)$$

This leads to the specification of the three components of the model:

1. **The forward model:** $g(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = J_{\text{int}}\mathbf{s}_{\text{int}} + \mathbf{J}_{\text{ext}}\mathbf{s}_{\text{ext}} + (\mathbf{z}_{\text{prior}} + \mathbf{A}b)$

The forward model is a linear model that makes deterministic predictions of XCH₄ and is outlined in Forward Model.

2. **The likelihood:** $p(\mathbf{z}|\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{z}|g(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$ with $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \sigma^2\mathbf{I}$

The predictions of XCH₄ made by $g(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ are evaluated against the XCH₄ observations using multivariate normal distributions.

Here, σ denotes the scalar standard deviation, and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \sigma^2\mathbf{I}$ is the corresponding diagonal covariance matrix. The value of $\sigma = 11$ ppb is chosen to represent the combined effect of instrument precision after aggregation and unresolved model error, including transport error. The likelihood assumes that observation errors are unbiased, normally distributed, and uncorrelated at the aggregation scale. Any residual spatial correlation or model structural error is absorbed into the effective error variance σ .

3. **The prior:** $p(\boldsymbol{\theta})$

The model has priors on all of its parameters, thereby encoding modeler assumptions about the distribution of emission rates, and the distribution of the background. These priors are described in Prior Distributions.

Posterior samples are generated using four independent MCMC chains. Each chain performs 1,000 warm-up iterations, during which the sampler adapts internal parameters and approaches the typical set of the posterior distribution. After warm-up, 1,000 additional iterations are drawn and retained as posterior samples.

Chains that exhibit divergent transitions are excluded from the analysis. Results are reported only for scenes where at least three chains complete without divergences.

3.2 Prior Distributions

The inversion is formulated in a Bayesian framework, requiring prior distributions for all inferred parameters. These priors encode assumptions about the magnitude and variability of methane emissions and background before considering the observations. In CORE, priors are specified for the background offset parameter b and for all emission rates.

3.2.1 Background Offset

MethaneSAT observations typically include regions that are minimally influenced by local emissions. These regions provide information about the background methane concentration defined in Background. In the forward model, the background is represented by an offset parameter b .

An initial estimate of methane enhancement is obtained from unaggregated L3 observations as:

$$\Delta z_i = z_i - z_{i,\text{prior}} \quad (5)$$

where z_i is the observed XCH₄ and $z_{i,\text{prior}}$ is the corresponding prior for the L2 XCH₄ retrieval at pixel i .

A set of candidate background offsets b_k are defined over the range between the 1st and 60th percentiles of the enhancement distribution $\Delta\mathbf{z}$. For each candidate offset, normalized residuals are computed as:

$$r_{i,k} = \frac{\Delta z_i - A_i b_k}{\sigma_i} \quad (6)$$

where A_i is the averaging kernel at pixel i and σ_i is the measurement standard deviation over a 20×20 pixel neighborhood centered on i .

Negative residuals are assumed to arise primarily from measurement noise, whereas positive residuals may be contaminated by emissions-driven enhancements. Therefore, for each candidate offset, only normalized residuals satisfying $r_{i,k} < 0$ are retained. These residuals are reflected about zero to form a symmetric distribution that approximates a standard normal distribution under the assumption of unbiased Gaussian noise.

The optimal background offset b_{best} is defined as the value that produces a reflected normalized residual distribution with a standard deviation closest to unity. Uncertainty in the background offset is estimated from the spread of candidate values that produce near-optimal fits. Specifically, the standard deviation σ_b is computed from the 10% of candidate offsets with the smallest deviation from unit variance, with a minimum value of 0.5 ppb imposed to prevent unrealistically small uncertainties.

The prior for the background offset is therefore defined as:

$$b \sim \mathcal{N}(b_{\text{best}}, \sigma_b^2) \quad (7)$$

Figure 7 illustrates the principle of the background estimation method. The prior XCH_4 field is adjusted by adding the term $\mathbf{A}b$ until it aligns with the lower envelope of the observations.

Figure 7: Original caption: Principle of the background estimation method. Left: The prior XCH_4 , $\mathbf{z}_{\text{prior}}$ (red), is increased by the term $\mathbf{A}b$ until it aligns with the lower envelope of the observations \mathbf{z} (green). Center: The optimal background offset is defined as the value of b for which the normalized standard deviation of observations below the background (red vertical line) matches the expected measurement precision. Right: Histogram of resulting enhancements, with negative values interpreted as measurement noise.

3.2.2 Emission

All emitter cells share the same prior distribution for methane emission rates. Emissions are modeled using a lognormal distribution:

$$\mathbf{s} \sim \text{LogNormal}(\mu, \sigma) \quad (8)$$

with parameters:

$\mu = -2.303$, $\sigma = 3.959(9)$ This distribution has a median emission rate of 0.1 kg h^{-1} and a 99th percentile of approximately $1,000 \text{ kg h}^{-1}$. The lognormal distribution allows the inversion

to represent a wide range of emission magnitudes while maintaining a reasonable expected mean. It assigns substantial probability to small emission rates while still permitting the large sources occasionally observed in methane production regions.

3.3 Output

CORE generates 4,000 posterior samples of the model state vector

$$\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\mathbf{s}_{\text{int}}, \mathbf{s}_{\text{ext}}, b) \quad (10)$$

which includes interior emission rates, exterior emission rates, and the background offset parameter.

Reported emissions correspond to the subset of interior emitters within the reported domain (see Model Domains). The expected emission rate for emitter i is estimated as the mean of the posterior samples:

$$s_i = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N s_{i,k} \quad (11)$$

where N is the number of posterior samples and $s_{i,k}$ is the sampled emission rate for emitter i in sample k .

Total emissions for a scene are computed by summing the emission rates of all emitters within the reported domain:

$$E_{\text{tot}} = \sum_i s_i \quad (12)$$

Figure 8 shows an example L4 emissions product, including the spatial distribution of inferred emissions and the total emission estimate with associated uncertainty. Emissions are spatially heterogeneous, with localized hotspots superimposed on a distributed background, illustrating the model’s ability to resolve both distinct and diffuse sources.

Figure 8: Original Caption: Example of the MethaneSAT L4 dispersed emissions product. Collection taken in California USA, 12 November, 2024 @ 22:14:46 UTC. For product format see Appendix A: Example Level-4 analysis product.

3.4 Uncertainty

CORE reports uncertainty in total emissions using two components. First, posterior uncertainty is derived from the Bayesian inversion. This includes uncertainty arising from measurement noise and the partitioning between interior emissions and inflow. The posterior uncertainty is summarized using the 95th percentile range of the sampled emission totals.

Second, an additional 20% empirical uncertainty is applied to account for meteorological transport errors introduced during Jacobian generation. These errors are not explicitly represented in the inverse model.

3.5 Interpretation Guidance

The L4 product reports posterior emission estimates and associated uncertainty metrics for each emitter within the reported domain. The structure of the output files is described in Appendix A: Example Level-4 analysis product. For algorithm limitations, refer to the associated document on the MethaneSAT data portal.

3.6 Interim Product

This is an algorithm-relevant excerpt from the limitations document:

Interim heatmap product reducing the bias due to noise-associated very small emissions.

We are currently releasing an interim heatmap product that reduces the influence of bias associated with small emissions that arise due to measurement noise, providing additional scenes. The method yields improved total-emission estimates by excluding likely-zero emitters. The procedure produces a conservative (strictly lower) estimate of total regional emissions which represents our current best estimate. However, the associated uncertainty intervals on the total regional emissions are uncharacterized: in particular, the upper bound to the total regional emission may be biased low.

A technical summary of this interim product is given below. The interim method uses a two-step workflow:

1. Compute spatially resolved fluxes across the full observed domain using the fully Bayesian method that we apply to each of our scenes.
2. Identify low-emission areas using a threshold on the emitter cell mean flux rate (currently 1 kg/h/km^2 , selected using the model selection criterion known as Widely Applicable Information Criterion (WAIC)). Areas below the threshold are assigned 0 kg/h/km^2 , effectively removing the cell as a predictor in the inverse model. We then recompute flux heatmap for the retained pixels using the same observations and report the updated emissions.

This two-step procedure reduces bias associated with sensor noise in very low or zero emission regions, giving a conservative (lower) estimate of total regional emissions while preserving the spatial pattern of the emissions from the original full Bayesian inverse model. The resulting emissions model simulates the observations very closely - often better than when all pixels were used as predictors-consistent with the WAIC concept. Because the interim product does not account for the post-selection step in the summary statistics, this approach does not preserve full uncertainty quantification for the complete domain and is considered an interim solution.

Notes

1. MethaneSAT acquired targeted scenes using a range of pointing geometries, resulting in variable swath width and ground pixel size; the median swath width was approximately 260 km and the median ground pixel size was $130 \text{ m} \times 400 \text{ m}$.
2. Other LPDM's widely used in atmospheric transport models for inverse modeling of trace gas emissions include HYSPLIT (Stein et al., 2015) and FLEXPART (Stohl et al., 2005).
 - HYSPLIT is commonly used for trajectory analysis and pollutant dispersion applications. However, it is not primarily designed for computation of source-receptor sensitivities within an inverse modeling framework. STILT uses HYSPLIT as the foundation for particle transport, but adds important features for directly computing influence functions that are compatible with Bayesian inference.

- FLEXPART provides a comprehensive representation of atmospheric transport and dispersion. It is widely used in regional and global studies. However, its configuration and computational requirements are more complex for routine processing of large satellite datasets.

4 Glossary

CORE (Column Observations to Regional Emissions): Bayesian inverse modeling framework used to estimate methane emissions from MethaneSAT observations.

4.1 Observations and Physical Quantities

XCH₄: Column-averaged dry-air mole fraction of methane.

Observation (\mathbf{z}): Vector of aggregated MethaneSAT XCH₄ measurements used in the inversion.

Prior XCH₄ ($\mathbf{z}_{\text{prior}}$): A priori estimate of XCH₄ used in the Level-2 retrieval, representing large-scale atmospheric structure.

Enhancement: Difference between observed and background methane concentration, defined as $\mathbf{z} - (\mathbf{z}_{\text{prior}} + \mathbf{A}b)$.

Background: XCH₄ in the absence of emissions within the modeled domain, represented as $\mathbf{z}_{\text{prior}} + \mathbf{A}b$.

Averaging kernel (\mathbf{A}): Dimensionless quantity describing the sensitivity of the retrieved methane column to the true atmospheric state.

4.2 Model Components

Forward model: Linear model relating emissions and background to observations: $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{J}_{\text{int}}\mathbf{s}_{\text{int}} + \mathbf{J}_{\text{ext}}\mathbf{s}_{\text{ext}} + (\mathbf{z}_{\text{prior}} + \mathbf{A}b)$.

Jacobian (\mathbf{J}): Matrix [number of observations \times number of emitters] describing the sensitivity of observations to emissions, where each element represents the change in observed methane concentration per unit emission.

Interior Jacobian (\mathbf{J}_{int}): Jacobian relating emissions within the interior domain to observations.

Exterior Jacobian (\mathbf{J}_{ext}): Jacobian relating emissions outside the interior domain to observations.

Emitter (emitter cell): A spatial grid cell for which methane emissions are estimated.

Pseudo-flux: A model parameter representing methane inflow from outside the interior domain, treated like an emitter but not necessarily corresponding to a distinct physical source.

Interior emissions (\mathbf{s}_{int}): Emission rates within the interior domain.

Exterior emissions (\mathbf{s}_{ext}): Emission rates outside the interior domain used to represent inflow.

Inflow: Contribution to observed methane concentrations from emissions outside the interior domain, represented by $\mathbf{J}_{\text{ext}}\mathbf{s}_{\text{ext}}$.

Receptor: A modeled observation location and volume used in atmospheric transport simulations to link emissions to observations.

Footprint: The sensitivity of a receptor to surface emissions, represented by a row of the Jacobian.

4.3 Spatial Domains

Data domain: Region containing valid MethaneSAT observations after filtering.

Interior domain: Region where emissions are directly constrained by observations.

Exterior domain: Region outside the interior domain that may influence observations through atmospheric transport.

Reported domain: Subset of the interior domain for which emission estimates are reported.

4.4 Inference and Statistics

State vector (θ): Vector of inferred model parameters, including emissions and background offset.

Posterior distribution: Probability distribution of model parameters conditioned on observations.

Prior distribution: Probability distribution representing assumptions about model parameters before considering observations.

Likelihood: Probability of observing the data given model parameters.

Posterior samples: Samples drawn from the posterior distribution using Markov Chain Monte Carlo.

Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC): Method for sampling from a probability distribution by constructing a Markov chain, which links different states using probabilities.

Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC): An MCMC method that uses gradient information to efficiently explore parameter space.

No-U-Turn Sampler (NUTS): An adaptive variant of HMC used to automatically tune sampling parameters.

Identifiability: The ability of the inversion to distinguish between different emission sources or between emissions and inflow based on the observations.

4.5 Output Quantities

Posterior mean emission: Expected emission rate for a gridcell, computed as the mean of posterior samples.

Total emissions: Sum of posterior mean emissions over all reported gridcells.

Uncertainty: Spread of posterior samples, typically summarized using percentile ranges.

4.6 Processing and Resolution

Level-2 (L2) product: Column-averaged dry-air mole fraction of methane (X_{CH_4}) and associated quantities (e.g., averaging kernels) derived from MethaneSAT radiance measurements.

Level-3 (L3) product: Gridded methane concentration product derived from Level-2 retrievals.

Level-4 (L4) product: Derived product containing inferred methane emissions.

Aggregation: Process of averaging L3 observations into coarser L4 gridcells.

5 Changelog

4 May 2026:

Updated description of MethaneSAT spectral characteristics in Section 1.1. Replaced the incorrect spectral sampling value (0.25 nm) with spectral dispersion (0.08 nm per pixel) and spectral resolution (0.23 nm FWHM). No impact on methodology or results.

6 References

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A Example Level-4 analysis product

```
dimensions:
  x = 114 ;
  y = 71 ;
variables:
  float x(x) ;
    x:long_name = "X coordinate in m UTM of the utm zone indicated by utm_crs_code" ;
    x:units = "m" ;
  float y(y) ;
    y:long_name = "Y coordinate in m UTM of the utm zone indicated by utm_crs_code" ;
    y:units = "m" ;
  double mean_flux(x, y) ;
    mean_flux:long_name = "Mean flux for each emitter, over all samples." ;
    mean_flux:units = "kg/hr" ;
  double lower_bound_flux(x, y) ;
    lower_bound_flux:long_name = "Lower bound on the 95% Confidence Interval of flux,
    per emitter." ;
    lower_bound_flux:units = "kg/hr" ;
  double upper_bound_flux(x, y) ;
    upper_bound_flux:long_name = "Upper bound on the 95% Confidence Interval of flux,
    per emitter." ;
    upper_bound_flux:units = "kg/hr" ;
  double mean_total_flux ;
    mean_total_flux:long_name = "Estimated total flux of entire reported domain, mean
    over all samples." ;
    mean_total_flux:units = "kg/hr" ;
  double total_flux_lower_bound ;
    total_flux_lower_bound:long_name = "Lower bound on the 95% confidence interval of
    the scene total." ;
    total_flux_lower_bound:units = "kg/hr" ;
  double total_flux_upper_bound ;
    total_flux_upper_bound:long_name = "Upper bound on the 95% confidence interval of
    the scene total." ;
    total_flux_upper_bound:units = "kg/hr" ;
  double target_total_flux_mean ;
    target_total_flux_mean:long_name = "Estimated total flux of target within reported
    domain, mean over all samples." ;
    target_total_flux_mean:units = "kg/hr" ;
  double target_total_flux_lower_bound ;
    target_total_flux_lower_bound:long_name = "Lower bound on the 95% confidence
    interval of the target total." ;
    target_total_flux_lower_bound:units = "kg/hr" ;
  double target_total_flux_upper_bound ;
    target_total_flux_upper_bound:long_name = "Upper bound on the 95% confidence
    interval of the target total." ;
    target_total_flux_upper_bound:units = "kg/hr" ;
  double flux_noise_floor ;
    flux_noise_floor:long_name = "Below this value, we believe fluxes are
    indistinguishable from 0 and should not be shown to users." ;
    flux_noise_floor:units = "kg/hr" ;
  double confidence_interval_scale_factor ;
    confidence_interval_scale_factor:long_name = "This is the error factor we believe
    comes from non-sampled error sources. It scales lower and upper bounds for CIs." ;
    confidence_interval_scale_factor:units = "1" ;

// global attributes:
```

```

:utm_crs_code = "epsg:32614" ;
:target_id = 5LL ;
:naming_authority = "data.methanesat.org" ;
:processor_version = "v0.7.6" ;
:id = "[prod]/core/t5/20240911/c01430050/p3500/output_grouper-precision-trimmed/
MSAT_L4_c01430050_p3500_v00007006_20240911T203025Z_203057Z.nc" ;
:date_created = "2025-09-21T15:30:36Z" ;
:platform = "MethaneSAT" ;
:collection_id = "01430050" ;
:processing_id = "3500" ;
:time_coverage_start = "2024-09-11T20:30:25.861125Z" ;
:time_coverage_end = "2024-09-11T20:30:57.803785Z" ;

group: ProcessingMetadata {
  // group attributes:
  :stilt_product = "[prod]/stilt/t5/20240911/c01430050/
MSAT_L4_Jacobian_c01430050_v00002002_20240911T203025Z.nc" ;
  :inversion_key = "data-domain:auto, jacobian:gfs, model-config:grouper-precision-
trimmed" ;
  :level3_product = "[prod]/regrid/t5/20240911/c01430050/p3260/45m/
MSAT_L3_45m_c01430050_p3260_v01014000_20240911T203025Z_203057Z.nc" ;
} // group ProcessingMetadata

```

B MethaneSAT Level-3 Product Fields Used in CORE

Table 2: MethaneSAT Level-3 product fields used in CORE

Field	Description
lat	Latitude of the pixel center (degrees)
lon	Longitude of the pixel center (degrees)
xch4	Column-averaged dry-air mole fraction of methane (ppb)
num_samples	Weighting variable from the L3 oversampling procedure representing the integrated spatial response of the spectrometer point spread function
apriori_data/xch4	L2 product retrieval a priori column-averaged dry-air mole fraction of methane
co2proxy_fit_diagnostics/ ch4_averaging_kernel_mean	Air-mass-weighted mean averaging kernel sensitivity of the methane retrieval
co2proxy_fit_diagnostics/ ch4_averaging_kernel_surface	Methane vertical column density averaging kernel for the surface level
co2proxy_fit_diagnostics/ ch4_averaging_kernel_mid_tropo	Methane vertical column density averaging kernel for a level in the mid-troposphere
co2proxy_fit_diagnostics/ ch4_averaging_kernel_mid_tropo_p	Pressure at the level used as mid-troposphere above